

Table 1. Plant characteristics of 4 selected breeding lines at Bambosa, Zaire, 1989-91.

Characteristic	Line/variety					
	R66	PR36-1-3-1	PR36-1-7-2	PR36-1-2-2	PR36-1-1-2	IRAT112 (check)
Life cycle (d)	124	116	116	116	115	115
Plant height (cm)	145	110	92	107	104	80
Lodging (score) ^a	3	1	1	1	1	1
Grain length (mm)	9.20	9.89	9.51	9.77	9.51	9.55
Grain width (mm)	2.98	3.24	3.07	3.12	3.07	2.88
Grain thickness (mm)	2.15	2.40	2.28	2.35	2.28	2.83
L-W ratio	3.08	3.05	3.09	3.13	3.09	3.32
W-T ratio	1.30	1.35	1.35	1.32	1.35	1.02
1,000-grain weight (g)	31.8	37.2	30.0	32.0	30.0	31.90
Translucency (%)	81.7	73.6	77.8	75.0	79.5	72.4
Disease reaction ^a						
Leaf blast	MS	MR	MR	MR	MR	MR
Leaf scald	MR	R	R	R	R	R
Grain yield (t/ha)	2.7	3.2	3.0	2.8	2.8	2.9

^aScored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

Table 2. Performance of 4 selected breeding lines at 3 locations. Zaire, 1989-91.

Location	Grain yield ^a (t/ha) and increase over check IRAT112 (%)									
	IRAT112 (check)		PR36-1-3-1		PR36-1-7-2		PR36-1-2-2		PR36-1-1-2	
	t/ha	%	t/ha	%	t/ha	%	t/ha	%	t/ha	%
Yangambi	2.8		2.8	3	2.7	0	2.5	-8	2.4	-13
Bambosa	2.9		3.2	11	3.0	4	2.8	-1	2.8	-1
Kiyaka	2.6		2.9	11	2.1	-10	2.8	10	2.9	11
Av	2.7		2.9	8	2.6	-5	2.7	1	2.7	-1

^aYield is av of 3 yr.

good grain quality. It resists blast and leaf scald and yields an average of 2.8 t/ha. The short stature (80 cm) of IRAT112, however, makes the common practice of hand harvesting difficult for tall farmers, who must stoop to harvest panicles. The result is that they tire quickly. They prefer a medium-height (100-140 cm) variety that is tolerant of lodging.

Local cultivar R66 was crossed with IRAT112 at Yangambi Research Station with the aim of creating a medium-height, lodging-tolerant, short-duration variety with good grain characteristics. Four breeding lines were selected from R66/IRAT112 and compared with IRAT112 at three sites (Yangambi, Bambosa, Kiyaka) from 1989 to 1991 (Table 1). The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Plots were 3 × 5 m, in

which 4-5 grains/hill were sown at 25 × 20-cm spacing.

At the Bambosa site, yield potential, life cycle, lodging tolerance, and reaction to leaf blast and leaf scald were similar for the breeding lines and IRAT112 (Table 1). Grain quality characteristics of the breeding lines, except for 1,000-grain weight, were also comparable with those of IRAT112. PR36-1-3-1 had an advantage over all other materials tested for 1,000-grain weight. Plant height, however, varied among lines, with PR36-1-3-1 averaging 110 cm. Performance of PR36-1-3-1 was good and yields stable across three locations (Table 2).

PR36-1-3-1 was released as Lioto to replace IRAT112. Increased plant height and tolerance for lodging are its major advantages over IRAT112. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

Brazilian Upland Rice Breeding Network: varietal release, time span, and yield increase

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The state rice research institutions of Brazil formed the Upland Rice Breeding Network in 1982 to develop suitable upland rice varieties for the country's different regions. The National Rice and Beans Research Center (CNPAP) coordinates the network.

Twelve upland varieties released between 1985 and 1989 were analyzed for time between crossing and varietal release, time required for yield trials, and average increase in grain yield of new materials compared with previously released varieties. Our primary information sources were publications containing data from varietal release trials prepared by state research institutions and CNPAP.

Time between crossing and varietal release averaged 8.8 yr (Table 1). The first variety released, Cuiabana, required

Table 1. Varieties released to the Brazilian Cerrados Region by the Upland Rice Breeding Network, 1985-89.^a

Variety	YC	YR	TD	YT	TY
Araguaia	1978	1987	9	1983	4
BR-4	1976	1985	9	1981	4
Cabaçu	1979	1988	9	1985	3
C. América	1978	1987	9	1983	4
Cuiabana	1978	1985	7	1983	2
Douradão	1978	1989	11	1986	3
EMCAPA 01	1976	1985	9	1981	4
Guaporé	1980	1988	8	1985	3
Guarani	1978	1987	9	1983	4
Rio Paranaíba	1978	1987	9	1984	3
Tangará	1981	1989	8	1985	4
Xingu	1980	1989	9	1986	3
Mean			8.8		3.4

^aYC = year of crossing, YR = year of release, TD = number of years from crossing to release, YT = year of trial, TY = number of years under yield trials.

Table 2. Average yields of varieties released to the Brazilian Cerrados Region by the Upland Rice Breeding Network compared across states and with checks.

Variety	State	Yield (t/ha)	Yield of check ^b (t/ha)	Yield increase (%)
Araguala	Goiás	2.9 (45) ^a	2.4 [1]	19
BR-4	Piauí	3.2 (6)	2.2 [1]	43
	Amapá	1.6 (3)	1.5 [1]	3
	Roraima	1.9 (4)	1.7 [1]	17
Cabaçu	Goiás	2.7 (36)	2.2 [1]	21
C. América	M. Grosso	2.3 (12)	2.2 [3]	6
Culabana	M. Grosso	1.7 (6)	1.4 [1]	18
Douradão	M. Gerais	3.0 (17)	2.4 [2]	25
EMCAPA 01	E. Santo	3.3 (6)	2.9 [1]	14
Guaporé	Rondonia	3.3 (8)	1.5 [1]	16
Guarani	M. Grosso	2.6 (12)	2.2 [3]	17
	M. Grosso Sul	2.2 (7)	2.1 [3]	6
	Goiás	3.2 (38)	2.7 [1]	16
	M. Gerais	2.5 (11)	1.9 [1]	31
Rlo Paranalba	M. Gross Sul	2.6 (7)	2.4 [1]	5
	Goiás	3.2 (38)	2.7 [1]	16
	M. Gerais	2.5 (11)	1.9 [1]	31
Tangará	M. Grosso	2.3 (21)	2.1 [3]	12
Xingu	Pará	2.5 (9)	2.1 [1]	18
Mean				17.3

^aNumbers in parentheses are number of yield trials. ^bNumbers in brackets represent check: 1 = IAC47, 2 = IAC25, 3 = IAC165.

only 7 yr. This reasonable amount of time was possible because the breeding program uses an off-season site.

Time required for yield trials averaged 3.4 yr, which was 38.6% of total time from crossing to release (Table 1).

Average years required provides a minimum for the safe interpretation of results before release. Yield trials in the Cerrados can be conducted only during the normal growing season and must be replicated over time to better assess the genotype × environment interaction.

We estimated regional yield increases from the network-released varieties by comparing grain yields of new varieties with those of checks in each trial. Percent yield increase was then added and divided by number of varieties, resulting in a 17.3% yield increase (Table 2). Overall mean (average yield of varieties and checks) showed a 20.9% increase. The average was 19.1% when number of trials was considered.

The network provided farmers with several new varieties from 1982 to 1989. Grain yield increased significantly as a result. Total upland rice production would increase by about 1 million t if all farmers used the new varieties on the 3.6 million ha planted to upland rice in Brazil, where current average yield is 1.3 t/ha. ■

Elite upland rice lines in Japan

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The importance of upland rice is decreasing in Japan. The largest upland rice area grown was 184,000 ha in 1960. Upland rice is now cultivated in rotation with vegetables on about 13,700 ha (0.7% of total cultivated rice area in Japan).

Systematic upland rice breeding in Japan was started in 1929. Since then, about 50 varieties have been bred and released to farmers. Most of the breeding materials came from Japanese traditional upland rice sources, a limited genetic pool.

We started screening for drought tolerance in indica and tropical japonica varieties in 1978 to increase genetic

Characteristics of Kanto-mochi 168 and Kanto-mochi 172, IAC, Japan.

Line/variety	Days to heading	Length (cm)		Blast resistance ^a		Yield (t/ha)
		Culm	Panicle	Leaf	Panicle	
Kanto-mochi 168	125	71	20.1	1	0	4.2
Kanto-mochi 172	126	76	20.5	0	0	4.5
Tsukubahatamochi	124	79	20.8	0	0	4.0

^aBlast resistance scored using scale where 0 = resistant and 9 = susceptible.

variation. We found some drought-tolerant traditional indica, African, and Chinese varieties and crossed them with Japanese upland varieties. Kanto-mochi 168 was bred in 1991 and Kanto-mochi 172 in 1992. (See table for important characteristics of these lines.) Kanto is the area code of our breeding team and mochi means glutinous in Japanese.

Kanto-mochi 168 was selected from the cross of JC81 (a traditional indica variety introduced from IRR) and Norin-mochi 4 (a Japanese upland variety) that was backcrossed twice.

Kanto-mochi 168 is more tolerant of water stress than Japanese varieties and has outstanding cooking quality.

Kanto-mochi 172 was bred from the cross of African upland rice variety IRAT109 and Japanese upland variety Tsukubahatamochi. The cooking quality of this line is not as good as that of other varieties, but its yield ability is excellent.

We are evaluating these lines in local adaptability tests. They will be useful genetic donors in future upland rice breeding. ■